

Designing and Implementing Telerehabilitation on Hand Skill Development for the Disabled People in Bangladesh

Md. Sami Uddin⁽¹⁾, Jahidul I. Khan⁽²⁾ and Hasan Mahmud⁽³⁾

(1) Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, Islamic University of Technology (IUT)

E-mail: Sami.cit06@Gmail.Com

(2) Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, Islamic University of Technology (IUT)

E-mail: Jikhan.cit.iut@Gmail.Com

(3) Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, Islamic University of Technology (IUT)

E-mail: Hasan.iut@Gmail.Com

ABSTRACT

A few organizations are working with the hand skill development for the disabled people in Bangladesh. Due to their limited scopes and facilities, they cannot cover the mass population of this country. Telerehabilitation can be introduced in this situation. The interaction between the therapist and the disabled people can take place via Telerehabilitation through video conferencing. So, our work aimed to design and implement such a system through User-Centred Design approach of Interaction design framework and a mock-up has been presented for the users of the system. At last a cognitive walkthrough analysis will be done to get the final functional activities of interaction as the result of the analysis.

Keywords: Interactive design process, video conferencing, Telerehabilitation, user centred design- UCD, cognitive walkthrough, Human Computer Interaction- HCI.

1- INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is a country with a population of 156 million [1]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that 10% [2] of the population of Bangladesh is disabled. Among them the number of people, suffering from hand skill disabilities, is quite high. Hand-Skill disability is a disease that can be caused [3] by cognitive impairment or by physical damage or accident. Patients cannot use their hands for normal activities. Hand skill development is the process of developing some techniques to overcome the problems of hand skill disability. Different types of therapies are given to the patients for developing their hand skills. As it demands the interaction between the patient and the therapist, Telerehabilitation [4] can play a major role in this

perspective. Telerehabilitation is the process of delivering the rehabilitation services over telecommunication networks and the Internet.

The paper begins with focusing on the condition of the existing therapy system that is being practised in Bangladesh. It also identifies the problems of current system and the opportunities of the development of Telerehabilitation on hand skill development in Bangladesh.

Then it proceeds by providing a discussion on the methodology/designing steps of "Interactive Design Process" [5] by following which we can design and implement the system software for the Telerehabilitation. The first phase of the design process describes the ways of identifying needs and establishing the requirements. It also contains contextual design (CD) and contextual inquiry (CI) which requires adequate user involvement. Then it continues with the alternative design procedures including User-Centred Design (UCD), design principles of UCD, consolidation and real-life scenario. UCD process is a standard approach of designing systems made by Human Computer Interaction (HCI). UCD is a design process in which the needs, wants and limitations of end-users are given the primary attention. A paper-based mock-up of the system is designed in this phase. Then the focus falls into the steps of building an interactive version/demo-version of the design. It contains the concept of video conferencing and system requirements for implementing the system. And finally, the concentration is on the evaluation of the system. It includes Cognitive walkthrough/Design walkthrough as a mean of evaluation technique which helps to make the system more user-friendly and realistic.

2- CONDITION OF THE EXISTING SYSTEM

People with disabilities both physical and cognitive, have to come to the organizations i.e. CRP (Centre for the Rehabilitation for the Paralyzed) in order to take the therapy. CRP works for these types of people and provides them the opportunity to live a better life. An opportunity was come to us to visit and observe the current system of therapy in CRP. From that observation of hand skill development therapy, the scenario of the hand skill rehabilitation system practiced over the country was generated. The focus was especially on the people facing problem with their hand skills. At first a therapist collects information about a patient and his/her previous medical records. Then the therapist selects therapies for that patient from the therapy list. For the hand skills development, the selected therapies are:

- Reaching: Ability to reach objects.
- Grasping: Ability to grasp any type of objects.
- Releasing: Ability to release the object from hand.
- Transferring: Transferring any object from one hand to another hand or place.

- Writing: Ability to write words or sentences.

The job of the therapist is to allocate the patient's sessions to give therapy. According to the schedule, the patients come to take the therapy. From the selected list, one task is selected by the therapist and the patient has to perform that task in front of him. For example, in the "grasping task" [6] there are some objects of different shapes in front of the patient. The therapist asks the patient to grasp one specific object. The therapist helps the patient to grasp that object if needed. The therapist observes the whole process and evaluates the progress of the patient after each session. The patient has to sit for the next therapy session according to the schedule.

3- PROBLEMS OF EXISTING SYSTEM & SOLUTION TO IT

For the therapy session, both the therapist and the patient have to sit together at the same time. This continuous process of giving therapy that has been described in the previous section, takes a lot of time and paper work. The patient has to come physically to the therapist in order to continue the therapy which costs a lot of money and time. It is a problematic process for them who reside in remote places to come and take the therapy. Sometimes it is almost impossible for some patients, who are physically severely damaged, to come to the therapist and take the therapy. Another major problem is that, the organizations, which provide these kinds of therapies, are very few in numbers. So, a large number of people are being deprived of this rehabilitation.

To minimize the problems that we have discussed in the earlier section, a lot of modifications of the existing system are needed. We want to deploy the remote therapy system in our project which will contribute to make the system a better one. The Hand-skill development system based on the telerehabilitation is our proposed solution. With the telerehabilitation system, many people can be provided with the therapy. So this system will give them a hope and chance to make their conditions better.

4- METHODOLOGY

Methodology describes the theoretical aspects and sequential steps to reach to the goal. For the design and implementation of the proposed system, "Interactive Design Process" has been followed as our methodology. In every step of this methodology, UCD (User Centred Design) [7] has been followed.

UCD is a design process in which the needs, expectations and satisfaction of the users of a system are given primary attention at every stage of the design process. Interactive Design Process consists of the following four sequential steps [8]:

4-1 IDENTIFYING NEEDS AND ESTABLISHING REQUIREMENTS

Place Contextual Design (CD) [9] is a user-centered design (UCD) process

developed by Hugh Beyer and Karen Holtzblatt. It incorporates ethnographic (comparative study of people) methods for gathering data relevant to the product, field studies, designing human-computer interfaces.

Contextual inquiry (CI), part of contextual design methodology, uses a well-defined set of procedures which includes conversations and interviewing the users [10] about their works in the real environment. The detailed behavior, expectations, mentality of the users are thoroughly observed and gathered so that the system's design interface can be the best design to be worked with.

Figure 1 Steps of Interactive Design Process

In the first phase, needs have been identified and established the requirements. The patients and the therapists were observed and interviewed in order to get a clear and detailed overview of the behavior, expectations and problems of them, ways of treating the patients, environment and instruments of the therapy, the Internet facility, users' knowledge about the computer, and condition of computer-based infrastructure- that is, the overall existing system. That is, contextual design (CD) and contextual inquiry (CI) based on UCD were used as observation tools.

4-2 DEVELOPING CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

After collecting the raw data from the first phase, these should be managed and processed according to their context. And from the grouped information, a conceptual design/ paper-based design is prepared.

After collecting the raw data from the users in the first phase, data are analysed and combined together in groups according to the similarity of their contents in order to reveal the common patterns. It is known as consolidation.

Norman (1988) [11] suggested that the following seven principles of design

are essential for facilitating the designer's task that would be followed by us: a) Use both knowledge in the world and knowledge in the head. b) Simplify the structure of tasks. c) Make things visible. d) Get the mappings right using graphics. e) Exploit the power of constraints, both natural and artificial. f) Design for error. g) Standardize.

From the information received in the previous phase, the data were consolidated. We accomplished this through the following steps:

- A single observation was written on each piece of paper.
- Individual notes were grouped according to the similarity of their contents.
- These groups were labeled with distinct colors which represent distinct levels in the hierarchy.
- Then the groups were combined with other groups to get the final result of the observations in a hierarchy.

A paper-based model of the overall system has been designed according to the UCD process and by using the consolidated data.

Paper-based model is a design model that is designed before the implementation phase. It contains the detailed design interface and functions that will be implemented as the interactive version of the design. It is basically a pen and paper model representing the overall view of the system.

Our paper-based model contains the following functionalities:

- 1) **Task Selection Panel:** There is a taskbar in the therapist interface containing the task list for the patients. There are five buttons containing tasks (reach, grasp, release, transfer, write). And every task contains also two more options: text and animation. By selecting any of these, task display panel is enabled at both users' end.
- 2) **Tasks Display Panel:** Text and animation are used for describing the selected task clearly to the patient. For "grasp> text", a text message will be displayed on this panel showing: "Grasp the Ball with your right hand". It will be displayed at both users' end.
- 3) **Text Chatting Panel:** There is an option for the text chatting between the therapist and the patient for the transmission of on-demand command or instruction. The family members/ friends can assist in the text chatting, if the patient is unable to do it.
- 4) **Video conferencing Panel:** For the interaction between the patient and the therapist, two-way simultaneous video and audio transmissions is needed which is done by the video conferencing. It contains two webcams for the patient end and one for the therapist end. In the patient end, one webcam is for the hand movement display and the other one is for the fa-

cial expression display. And the patient will see the view of the therapist.

5) Interactive buttons: The buttons are for performing the functional activities; i.e. selecting tasks from task selection panel, Send button to send the text in text chatting panel etc.

Figure 2 Paper-based model of the therapist's interface

6) Timer: The timer is used for managing the sessions maintained by the therapist. The timer starts when the therapy starts and ends when it finishes.

Figure 3 Paper-based model of the patient's interface

7) Output Panel: There will be an output panel for displaying the output of the patient's writing. The patient will use a Tablet PC and a stylus connected with computer via Bluetooth. There are three buttons: Try Again, OK,

and Save buttons for evaluating the writing of the patient. First one is for the retaking the task; second one for notifying the patient if he can complete the task successfully; last one for saving the output for future evaluation.

Tablet PC is a specialized device that enables the users to write on touch-sensitive screen with the stylus (specialized pen to write on). It is specially designed to take the hand-written inputs on the screen. As in this proposed system, the patients have to write by hand, Tablet PC will serve the purpose for that occasion. This is an input device for the patient and its output will be displayed in the therapist's end.

Figure 4 Scenarios of the on-going therapy

A scenario [12] helps to understand the functionality of the paper-based model that we have designed.

- Context: Specially organized room with computer system, webcam, sound system, various shapes of objects for therapy, stylus, Internet connection.
- Actors: Maria is a girl having disability with her hand; Maisha is a therapist; Bushra is the sister of Maria who is a helping hand for Maria.
- Rationale: This scenario illustrates how our system develops the hand skill of Maria through the Telerehabilitation.

Maria is sitting in front of her computer at her home with her sister Bushra for helping her in the time of therapy. And a therapist, Maisha is in the CRP. According to the schedule, Maisha starts the therapy session with Maria. Bushra is operating the computer for Maria to continue the session. Maria and Maisha can see each other through the webcams. Now, Maisha selects the writing task from the task selection panel. Then she selects to write the word "Bangladesh" and it will be appeared into the Maria's terminal. Besides, the letter wise pen movement will be animated to Maria for making the writing easier for her. While Maria is performing the task, Maisha can observe her facial expression and hand movement using two separate webcams. If Maria faces some problems while writing, Bushra let Maisha know the problems by text chatting panel. Bushra can help Maria in writing, if needed. If Maisha finds any problem, she informs Bushra to take necessary steps using text chatting panel. The writing of Maria is displayed in the specified display panel of the software. After seeing the writing accuracy, Maisha will evaluate Maria's development and keep track of the progress of Maria.

4-3 BUILDING INTERACTIVE VERSION OF THE DESIGN

In this phase, an interactive version (demo-version) of the software was developed in which the patient can feel the real-life experience of the software system by using it and providing feedback accordingly. This interactive version helps both the patients and the therapists to be adapted into a new system.

According to the paper based model the interactive version of the system has been developed. Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF), C# and XAML have been selected to use as the implementation tools in Windows platform. The following specifications have been chosen to develop the demo-version of the design:

1) Video conferencing: For implementing the video conferencing [13], a camera (to capture local video), a video display (to display remote video), a microphone (to capture local audio), and speakers (to play remote audio) are needed. In addition to these more obvious components, a video conferencing terminal also includes a codec ("COmpressor/DECompressor") for compressing and decompressing audio and video information, a user interface, a computer system to run on, and a network connection.

2) Webcam: Webcam [14] comes with an image sensor, which gives adequate image quality. The resolution of our webcam is 1.3 MP as it is a minimum for video conferencing for bandwidth consumption in our country.

3) Codecs: H.323 [15] is a multimedia communication standard produced by ITU (International Telecommunications Union). In H.323, the end points compress audio and video data to be exchanged in a less network bandwidth environment. It is specially designed to offload the compression and decompression task from the PC, allowing the endpoints to achieve a good overall performance.

Figure 5 Interactive version of the system – patient end

4) Bandwidth consideration: An encoding rate of 384 Kbps (64 Kbps for the audio and 320 Kbps for the video) is common. The 384 Kbps stream is compressed and sent to the remote endpoint and same is received from the remote end point. Thus approximately, for the worst case 384×2 Kbps full duplex bandwidth [16] is required to support the video-conference for the end points.

Figure 6 Interactive version of the system – Therapist end

Computer system requirements- 1 gigahertz (GHz) or faster 32-bit (x86) or 64-bit (x64) processor, 512 megabyte (MB) RAM or more, Windows XP or later version

of Operating System, 1 gigabyte (GB) Hard disk or more, DirectX 9 supported graphics, 15 inch monitor (CRT/LCD), LAN Card, speaker, microphone, 1.3 MP webcam, any Tablet PC having display size 10 inch (minimum).

Figure 7 Interactive version of the system – Task Management

In the interactive version of the system there are three parts. Patient’s part, Therapist’s part and the Task Management part. Patient can see the Therapist and can only able to see the task that is assigned by the Therapist. There is also a panel for text chatting in the Patient’s part. The Therapist handles the whole process of this system. She/he can see the Patient through the web-cam. Therapist can edit and assign. For that there is a panel for editing task in the Therapist’s part. Other part is the task management part which can be customised according to patient. In one part it displays the information of the patient and in the rest of the parts the therapist can select task from the available list and can save the completed tasks in the done list.

4-4 EVALUATION OF THE DESIGN

After the development of the interactive version of the system software, the evaluation takes place. Evaluation is an essential part of the “Interactive design process” because it ensures user-satisfaction and correctness of the system software.

Design walkthrough (Cognitive walkthrough) [17] is an evaluation technique that has been followed. At this technique, the users (therapist and patient) perform the walkthrough by being them asked a set of questions for each sub-task (a small part of the whole system software, i.e. taskbar, video-conferencing window). Typically four questions were asked:

- Will the user try to achieve the effect that the sub-task has? Does the user understand that this sub-task is needed to reach the user's goal?
- Will the user notice that the correct action is available? E.g. is the button visible?
- Will the user understand that the wanted sub-task can be achieved by the action? E.g. the right button is visible but the user does not understand the text and will therefore not click on it.
- Does the user get feedback? Will the user know that they have done the right thing after performing the action?

We asked four questions of the Cognitive Walkthrough's concept for each of the functionalities of our developed system. After the evaluation has been done, the feedback from the users was gathered. Based on the feedback; the system design has been modified by the following way:

- At first, the users had more controls in their interface. It created some problems such as users are not sufficiently knowledgeable of computer operations. So they frequently made mistakes while operating this software. For example, before users could control starting and stopping the text chatting panel. But in the present design, the text chatting panel automatically loads when the system starts. Users can just type in the text chatting panel.
- At first, the webcam displaying panel was a little one. But according to the demands of the users, the display panel has been enlarged.
- In the former design, the whole tasks were grouped into five broad groups: Reach, Grasp, Write, Transfer and Release. And each type had its own sub-tasks. However, the therapists demanded a list containing all the sorted tasks to be shown into the main interface.
- There is a separate window containing the patient's info, picture and tasks edit panel. The available, selected and done task lists are saved for future usage.

5- CONCLUSION

The computerized therapy system for hand-skill rehabilitation will make the whole therapy system easier, more efficient and more flexible. As we have used the currently available technologies and devices, it will not cost any extra money for it. At the same time, it will save the travelling cost of the patient as the patient can get the full treatment at home. The User-Centered Design (UCD) model has been used to design and develop the overall system. So, the user gets the number one priority and users' satisfaction is the prior issue. In every step of this design and implementation, we tried to involve the users to make the desired system.

This is the first approach of introducing the telerehabilitation system on hand-skill development in Bangladesh. It is just the beginning. This system needs lots of development so that it can contribute in the health sector. The future plan is to extend the functionalities of this developed system. Another plan is to introduce some devices that can be used for giving the therapy, such as specialized pens, gloves, touch-sensitive display, tablet PC etc. as input and output devices in this present developed system. In summary, we want to use all the available latest technologies in this developed system software.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We wish to acknowledge the authority of Centre for the Rehabilitation of the Paralysed (CRP), Bangladesh, especially the Occupational Therapy Department. We would like to thank them for giving us the opportunity to observe their patients with hand skill disabilities, infrastructure, overall therapy system-which helped us a lot to better understand the current system and to design this system accordingly.

REFERENCES

- [1] CIA World Factbook, 2010.
- [2] World Health Organization (WHO). Available: "www.who.int/en/"
- [3] American Association on Intellectual and Development Disabilities. Available: www.aamr.org.
- [4] D. Theodoros and T. Russell, "Telerehabilitation: current perspectives", *Stud Health Technol Inform*, pp. 132:191-209, 2008.
- [5] H. Sharp, Y. Rogers, and J. Preece., *Interaction design: beyond human-computer interaction*. 2nd Ed, Wiley, 2007.
- [6] J. C. Smith, P. N. Pratt, and A. S. Allen., *Occupational therapy for children*, C.V. Mosby, 1989.
- [7] C. Abras, D. Maloney-Krichmar, J. Preece, "User-Centered Design". In Bainbridge, W. *Encyclopedia of Human-Computer Interaction*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, 2004.
- [8] A. Dix, J. Finlay, G. D. R. Beale, *Human Computer Interaction*. 3rd Ed. Prentice Hall, 2003.
- [9] H. Beyer and K. Holtzblatt, *Contextual Design: Defining Customer-Centred Systems*. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann. ISBN: 1-55860-411-1. 1998.

- [10] S. Kujala and M. Kauppinen, "Identifying and Selecting Users for User-Centered Design", Helsinki University of Technology. Proc. of the third Nordic conference on Human-computer interaction (NordiCHI '04), pp. 297-303, 2004.
- [11] D. Norman, *The design of everyday things*. New York: Double-Day, 1988.
- [12] M. Richard, Young, P. Barnard, "The use of scenarios in human-computer interaction research: turbocharging the tortoise of cumulative science", *ACM SIGCHI Bulletin*, 1987.
- [13] *Videoconferencing Cookbook, Version 4.1*, Video Development Initiative (ViDe) et al. Available: <http://www.vide.net/>. 2004-5.
- [14] E. Parker, *The little Web cam book*, 1st Ed, Pearson Education, 1999.
- [15] ITU-T Recommendation H.323, *Packet-based multimedia communication systems*. Available: <http://www.itu.int/>. 2006.
- [16] *Networks Matters, Videoconferencing Cookbook, Version 4.1*, Video Development Initiative (ViDe) et al. Available: <http://www.vide.net/>. 2004-5.
- [17] C. Wharton et al., "The cognitive walkthrough method: a practitioner's guide", in J. Nielsen & R. Mack *Usability Inspection Methods*, pp.105-140.